

System Reduction by Eigen Permutation Algorithm and Improved Pade Approximations

Authors : Jay Singh*, C.B.Vishwakarma**, Kalyan Chatterjee***

Abstract : A mixed method by combining a Eigen permutation algorithm and improved pade approximations is proposed for reducing the order of the large-scale dynamic systems. The most dominant Eigen value of both original and reduced order systems remain same in this method. The proposed method guarantees stability of the reduced model if the original high-order system is stable and is comparable in quality with the other well known existing order reduction methods. The superiority of the proposed method is shown through examples taken from the literature.

Keywords : Eigen permutation algorithm; Order reduction; improved pade approximations; Stability; Transfer function.

Conference Title : ICEP 2014 : International Conference on Electronic Publications

Conference Location : journal city, WASET

Conference Dates : November 23-23, 2014